

**Open Research Case Study
Lancaster University**

**No rejection allowed: a toxicology
journal's radical policy for promoting
equity and collaboration in open research**

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No rejection allowed: a toxicology journal's radical policy for promoting equity and collaboration in open research

Context

Equality of participation is a key goal of open research. However, successfully utilizing open research practices requires specialist skills and knowledge. Because of inequalities in the way researchers are exposed to and trained in open research, there is a paradoxical risk of creating a potentially exclusionary open research system.

Evidence-Based Toxicology (EBT) was established in 2023 as the first dedicated open science journal in toxicology, implementing a full range of open research policies including Registered Reports, preprinting, open access, community engagement, sharing data and code, and collaborative open peer review. EBT's standards for open research are radically high for toxicology, and put the journal at risk of being unintentionally exclusionary.

Here we describe EBT's radical "no reject" policy, showing how it addresses risk of inequity in open science publishing, in a way that unlocks a cascade of collaborative open research practices (in **bold**), while demonstrating a model for commercial publishing that is neither exploitative nor a drain on the academic system.

Policy

EBT's **no-reject** policy means editors are not permitted to desk-reject a submission, i.e. that every submission must be evaluated and feedback sent to the submitting authors. Only unethical and out-of-scope submissions are excluded from this policy. Since EBT cannot reject submissions, all authors have equal opportunity to experience and learn an end-to-end, radically open publishing process.

Of course, EBT cannot peer-review everything: peer-review is a finite resource that journals need to protect. Peer-review is also unreliable for enforcing publishing standards (1). EBT therefore combines its no-reject policy with **rigorous editorial triage**, whereby trained handling editors utilize modular checklists to consistently and comprehensively check submitted manuscripts for coherence, completeness, and compliance with EBT's open research policies. Manuscripts are only sent out for peer-review after passing these detailed

checks. Manuscripts that fall short are revised in **collaborative review** between authors and the handling editor.

Since EBT is gatekeeping against a high standard for publication, the journal needs to be transparent and accountable. EBT therefore requires authors to make their submissions available as **preprints** before editors will evaluate them. EBT then publishes on its Zenodo Community evaluation reports for each round of **open manuscript review** (2). Reports are compiled by handling editors to ensure constructiveness and provide guidance. Peer-reviewers are given the option to be **credited** as co-authors of evaluations using their ORCID.

Thus, a no-reject policy initiates a cascade of open research publishing practices at EBT.

Benefits

No-reject combined with detailed triage and open review promotes fair, constructive, public comment. This makes publishing in EBT a valuable service to authors (improving their manuscript), peer-reviewers (their time is well-used and they can be credited for their work), and the reader (they can see the scientific issues raised during review). Such a value-for-service approach addresses important criticisms that commercial publishing is an exploitative drain on academia (3).

No-reject policies are especially beneficial to marginalised or less experienced groups. EBT has worked on many submissions by NGOs, people outside the US and EU, and early career researchers that, instead of being rejected as low quality and potentially put at risk of exploitation by predatory publishers, have successfully been published as high-quality open research manuscripts.

Challenges

The major challenge is financial. EBT's level of attention takes time, which costs money in salaries or honoraria (EBT **pays its editors**). To generate revenue, EBT charges authors on a **Gold Open Access** APC model. Diamond OA is not currently feasible for EBT.

Because EBT has high acceptance rates from its collaborative review model, journal revenue scales with effort. This neutralises how Gold OA incentivises inflation of publication rates

while deflating the quality of published manuscripts (4). We also provide APC waivers and reductions to support authors. Nonetheless, EBT primarily operates on a “pay-to-play” model.

To respond, we plan to support the implementation of our publishing model in regions where costs are commensurate with regional capacity to pay, rather than requiring researchers in low- or middle-income countries to afford services located in high-income countries.

Learning

By treating no-reject as the foundation of a radical suite of editorial policies that welcome researchers of all backgrounds, EBT has shown that journals do not have to be a drain on academia but can deeply support open research practices.

References

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